

Research article

Inhibition of NH₃-SCR over Cu-CHA at high partial pressures of water: Measurements and DFT-based kinetic modeling

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ABSTRACT

Cu-exchanged chabazite (Cu-CHA) is a widely applied catalyst for selective catalytic reduction of nitrogen oxides in oxygen excess. The application of Cu-CHA to exhaust from H₂-fueled engines depends on the behavior of this material at high partial pressures of water. We have performed flow-reactor measurements, which show that the NO_x conversion at 200 °C over a Cu-CHA (3.2 wt% Cu, Si/Al=6.7) catalyst decreases with increasing partial pressures of water from 2 to 25%. Simultaneously, the apparent reaction order in water decreases from -0.17 to -1.18, following the simple empirical equation $-3.43(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/p^{\circ})^{0.76}$. The experimental results are corroborated with DFT-based microkinetic modeling. The DFT calculations show that H₂O competes with NO adsorption on the Cu-sites and hinders the reaction. The kinetic model describes accurately the inhibiting effect of water after minor adjustments to the computed Gibbs free energies of water adsorption.

1. Introduction

Selective catalytic reduction of NO_x using ammonia as reducing agent (NH₃-SCR) is the leading technology for NO_x control in oxygen excess, such as diesel exhausts [1]. Cu-exchanged small-pore chabazite zeolites have shown favorable low-temperature activity for NH₃-SCR and good hydrothermal stability at high temperatures [1–3]. The main NO_x component in lean-burn engine exhausts is NO and the NH₃-SCR reaction follows in this case the, so-called, standard SCR-reaction:

The reaction consumes equal amounts of NO and NH₃. O₂ is required to accommodate the hydrogen atoms in NH₃. The NH₃-SCR reaction is a redox reaction that proceeds via alternating oxidation and reduction steps where Cu changes oxidation state between Cu^I and Cu^{II}. O₂ adsorbs on Cu^I sites forming Cu^{II}, whereas the coupling between NO and NH₃ reduces Cu^{II} to Cu^I.

The Cu-ions are solvated by NH₃ at temperatures below 300 °C and the reaction proceeds over mobile [Cu(NH₃)₂]⁺ complexes [4–12]. The mobility of the complexes is critical as it facilitates the formation of pairs of complexes that are required to activate O₂ [10,13,14]. O₂ adsorption results in a [Cu₂(NH₃)₄O₂]²⁺ peroxy-species, which is a key intermediate as it enables NO adsorption. In subsequent steps, adsorbed NO reacts with NH₃ forming H₂NNO and HONO. The H₂NNO and HONO intermediates decompose with low barriers to N₂ and H₂O water over Brønsted acid sites [15,16].

A density functional theory (DFT) based microkinetic model [16] has revealed different roles of NH₃ during the reaction: (i) NH₃ is a ligand that solvates the Cu-ions, which enhances the mobility of the [Cu(NH₃)₂]⁺ complex and enables O₂ activation, (ii) NH₃ from the gas-phase is a reactant that couples to NO, and (iii) NH₃ inhibits the reaction by competing with NO for adsorption on the [Cu₂(NH₃)₄O₂]²⁺ peroxy-species. The inhibition effect of NH₃ is evident from the measured and calculated small negative reaction order (about -0.2) of the reaction with respect to NH₃ [16]. The NH₃-inhibition makes the NO adsorption step rate controlling at low temperatures. [16]

Cu-ions in CHA are solvated by H₂O in H₂O-only atmospheres [9]. As the character of the H₂O bonding to metal ions is similar to that of NH₃, it can be expected that H₂O also inhibits the NH₃-SCR reaction. Inhibition by H₂O is particularly important in connection with H₂ fueled combustion engines, which typically contains 20%–25% H₂O in the exhaust, corresponding to 2–5 times the typical H₂O concentrations in diesel exhausts. To assess whether traditional SCR catalysts can also be used for H₂-fueled engines, it is necessary to understand the impact of high water concentrations on the NH₃-SCR performance of Cu-CHA. The reports regarding the effect of H₂O on the NH₃-SCR reaction over Cu-CHA are currently inconsistent. While some studies report a promoting effect [17,18] of H₂O, others have observed an inhibiting effects, particularly at low temperatures [18,19].

Herein, we present measurements of the NH₃-SCR rate over Cu-CHA with H₂O partial pressures in the range from 2% to 25%. The

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measurements are corroborated with Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations and DFT-based microkinetic modeling to understand the atomic-scale mechanisms of how H₂O affects the NH₃-SCR reaction. H₂O is found to inhibit the reaction and the reaction order in water becomes increasingly negative with increasing partial pressures of water. The DFT calculations reveal that the NO, NH₃ and H₂O adsorption energies are similar on the [Cu₂(NH₃)₄O₂]²⁺ and [Cu₂(NH₃)₄(OH)₂]²⁺ intermediates. The DFT based microkinetic model reproduces accurately the experimental data after minor adjustments of the computed Gibbs free energies of water adsorption.

2. Experimental and computational details

The dependence of the SCR activity of Cu-CHA catalysts on the water content is investigated for a Cu-CHA catalyst with an Si/Al ratio of 6.7, a Cu loading of 3.2 wt%. The Cu-CHA catalysts are synthesized by impregnating H-CHA zeolite materials with an appropriate amount of Cu-nitrate solution, followed by calcination at 600 °C for 2 h. The H-CHA zeolite materials are commercial and obtained from Umicore. A sample of 4 mg of the catalyst (sieve fraction 150-300 μm) is mixed with 76 mg of SiC and loaded into a quartz U-tube reactor with a 4 mm internal diameter. The sample is degreened prior the measurements by exposing the sample to 10% O₂ for 30 min at 500 °C. Activity measurements are conducted using 4 mg of catalyst material, exposed to a gas mixture comprising 500 ppm of NO, 600 ppm of NH₃, 10% O₂, and partial pressures of water ranging from 2% to 25%, at 200, °C in an N₂ carrier gas with a total flow rate of 18 NL/h. The concentrations of NO, NO₂, and N₂O are monitored using a Gasetm CX4000 FTIR spectrometer.

The effect of water on the NH₃-SCR kinetics is reflected in an apparent reaction order of the NH₃-SCR rate, which essentially expresses the dependence of the rate constant on the partial pressures of water. The apparent reaction order in H₂O is determined by assuming that the rate of NO conversion (r_{NO}) can be expressed as:

$$r_{\text{NO}} = k P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} P_{\text{O}_2}^{n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} P_{\text{NO}}^{n_{\text{NO}}} P_{\text{NH}_3}^{n_{\text{NH}_3}} \quad (1)$$

The concentrations of O₂ and H₂O are high and can, therefore, be considered as constant during the measurement. In this way, it is possible to define an effective rate constant $k' = k P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} P_{\text{O}_2}^{n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}$ such that:

$$r_{\text{NO}} = k' P_{\text{NO}}^{n_{\text{NO}}} P_{\text{NH}_3}^{n_{\text{NH}_3}} \quad (2)$$

For the kinetic analysis, a commonly used approximation is to assume that the NH₃-SCR reaction is first order in NO and zeroth order in NH₃ [20–22]. The rate constant k' (mol/g h) can under these assumptions be evaluated as:

$$k' = -\frac{F \ln(1 - X_{\text{NO}})}{W} \quad (3)$$

where, F is the molar flow (mol/h), X_{NO} is the NO conversion, and W is the amount of catalyst (g). The reaction order for H₂O is determined as the slope of the natural logarithm of k' with respect to the natural logarithm of the partial pressure of water.

The experimentally determined reaction orders for H₂O are compared to results from a DFT-based microkinetic model. Spin-polarized DFT calculations are performed using the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP) [23–26]. A plane wave basis set is used to describe the valence electrons with a cutoff energy of 480 eV. The interaction between the valence and the core electrons is described with the projector augmented wave (PAW) method [27,28]. The explicitly treated valence electrons are Cu(11), Si(4), Al(3), O(6), N(5), and H(1). The k-point sampling is restricted to the gamma point.

The gradient-corrected Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) [29] functional augmented with a Hubbard-U term and van der Waals corrections [30,31] is used to describe exchange–correlation effects. Calculations on enzymatic systems with known structures and a similar

Cu-OO-Cu core as the [Cu₂(NH₃)₄O₂]²⁺-peroxo complex have shown that a Hubbard-U (6 eV) term for Cu 3d is needed to account for the charge separation in the Cu-O bond [32,33]. The electronic structure is considered to be converged when the difference between steps in the Self-Consistent Field loop is lower than 1×10^{-5} eV. Structures are considered to be relaxed when the force acting on each atom is smaller than 0.02 eV/Å. Water adsorption on the [Cu₂(NH₃)₄O₂]²⁺-peroxo complex is investigated for all four Cu-positions. Initial structural optimizations are followed by about 5 ps molecular dynamics simulations (300 K). The reported structures are structural relaxations from the molecular dynamics trajectories. The chabazite structure is described with a periodic rhombohedral unit cell, which contains 12 tetrahedral Si-sites. We use the experimentally determined lattice parameters $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 94.2^\circ$, $a = b = c = 9.42$ Å, which are fixed during the structural optimizations. To model Cu-exchanged CHA, two Si atoms in the 6-membered ring of the zeolite cages are replaced by Al yielding an Si/Al ratio of 5. The ratio is similar to the value used in the experiments.

Mean-field microkinetic modeling is used to explore the consequences of the DFT reaction landscapes and facilitate comparison to experiments. The present model extends our previous model [16] by adding steps for H₂O adsorption and NH₃ adsorption on a [Cu₂(NH₃)₄(OH)₂]²⁺ intermediate. The steady-state reaction rates and fractional intermediate concentrations are obtained by solving a set of coupled ordinary differential equations:

$$\frac{d\theta_i}{dt} = \sum_j c_{ji} r_j(\vec{\theta}) \quad (4)$$

where each intermediate i has a fractional concentration θ_i , r_j is the elementary reaction rates, which depend on the fractional concentration of the intermediates ($\vec{\theta}$). c_{ji} is the stoichiometric constant of compound i in reaction j . The rate constant (k_j) for the reaction j is given by [34]:

$$k_j = \frac{k_{\text{B}} T}{h} e^{-\Delta H^\ddagger/k_{\text{B}} T} e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/k_{\text{B}}} \approx \frac{k_{\text{B}} T}{h} e^{-\Delta E^\ddagger/k_{\text{B}} T} e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/k_{\text{B}}} \quad (5)$$

where k_{B} is Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature, and h is Planck's constant. ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger are the difference between initial and transition state for enthalpy and entropy, respectively. The change in enthalpy (ΔH^\ddagger) is replaced with the change in energy (ΔE^\ddagger) as the volume and pressure are unchanged during the reaction. The entropies for the gas phase molecules are calculated from the translational, rotational, and vibrational partition functions. For adsorbed molecules, only the vibrational partition function is used, and the translations and rotations are described as frustrated vibrations. The vibrational modes are evaluated in the harmonic approximation [16]. The NO turnover frequency (TOF) is calculated by summing the elementary steps that consume NO and is reported per Cu-ion and second.

3. Results and discussion

To investigate the temperature dependent effect of H₂O on the NH₃-SCR reaction, we measure the NO_x conversion under dry (no H₂O) and wet conditions (5% H₂O) in a temperature interval from 160 °C to 300 °C, Fig. 1(A). The NO_x conversion is below 20% at 160 °C and increases with temperature to full conversion at 260 °C. The presence of water clearly inhibits the NO_x conversion up to a temperature of about 260 °C. It is possible that water affects the reaction also above 260 °C, which in that case is masked by the complete conversion.

To study the dependence of the catalyst activity on partial pressures of water, we measure the NO_x conversion at 200 °C with partial pressures of water from 2% to 25%, Fig. 1(B). The case without water is also included. The NO_x conversion has a steady decline from 2% to 25% of partial pressures of water. Previous studies on the effect of H₂O on the SCR-activity over Cu-CHA have mainly compared dry conditions with water concentrations of a few percent. However, these reports are not consistent as both promoting [17,18] and inhibiting [18,19] effects have been reported. The results for 0% and 2% water in Fig. 1(B) may

Fig. 1. (A) NO conversion as a function of temperature at SCR conditions with 5% H₂O and without H₂O is measured using 10 mg of sample and exposed to a gas mixture comprising 500 ppm of NO, 600 ppm of NH₃, 10% O₂, and 5% H₂O (Wet case). (B) NO conversion at 200 °C as a function of partial pressures of water is measured using 4 mg of the catalyst, exposed to a gas mixture comprising 500 ppm of NO, 600 ppm of NH₃, 10% O₂, and partial pressures of water ranging from 2% to 25%, at 200, °C in a N₂ carrier gas with a total flow rate of 18 NL/h.

indicate a promotional effect of water at low concentrations. However, as different calibrations are used in dry and wet conditions, we are not certain about this result.

The rate constant for the NH₃-SCR reaction is calculated for partial pressures of water in the range from 2% to 25% with the assumption that the SCR reaction follows first-order kinetics with respect to NO and zeroth-order kinetics with respect to NH₃. The NO conversion decreases continuously with increasing partial pressures of water, which is reflected in a decreasing first-order rate constant with increasing partial pressure of water.

The natural logarithm of the rate constant $\ln(k')$ as a function of natural logarithm of the partial pressure of water $\ln(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/p^\circ)$ is presented in Fig. 2. The decrease in natural logarithm of the rate constant with increasing partial pressures of water can be described by an empirical function $f(x) = a e^{bx} + c$ where $x = \ln(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/p^\circ)$. The fitted parameters are $a = -4.51$, $b = 0.76$, $c = 4.91$ and the R² value is 0.973. The derivative of $\ln(k')$ with respect to $\ln(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$ gives the reaction order in water as a function of partial pressures of water: $f'(x) = a b e^{bx} = -3.43 (p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/p^\circ)^{0.76}$ (see inset Fig. 2). The reaction order decreases from -0.17 to -1.18 as the partial pressure of water increases from 2% to 25%, which reflects a pronounced inhibition of water at high partial pressures.

To investigate the reason for water inhibition of the NH₃-SCR reaction at high partial pressures of H₂O, we compare the experimentally

Fig. 2. Natural logarithm of the rate constant ($\ln(k')$) as a function of the natural logarithm of partial pressures of water ($\ln(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/p^\circ)$). The solid line is an empirical fit to the experimental data and the dashed line is a fit with a Langmuir-type of expression. The inset shows the reaction order in H₂O as a function of the partial pressures of water for the empirical fit and the Langmuir model. Activity is measured with 4 mg of catalyst under exposure to a gas mixture of 500 ppm NO, 600 ppm NH₃, and 10% O₂, with partial pressures of water from 2% to 25% at 200 °C, in a N₂ carrier gas at 18 NL/h flow rate.

measured reaction orders with results from a DFT-based microkinetic model. The present kinetic model is based on a previously suggested reaction cycle [15,16], as shown in Fig. 3. The reaction cycle assumes a pair of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2]^+$ complexes in one CHA cage over which O₂ adsorbs forming a $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ peroxy-species. NO adsorbs on one of the Cu cations forming NO-OO*. NH₃ couples to the adsorbed NO forming H₂NNO. The NO-NH₃ coupling is repeated, yielding a $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ complex. The $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ complex reacts twice with NO, forming two HONO species and two linear $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2]^+$ complexes, which completes the reaction cycle. H₂NNO and HONO+NH₃ are decomposed to N₂ and H₂O over a Brønsted acid site. Unwanted N₂O formation competes with the NH₃-SCR reaction (reaction 16). Moreover, NH₃ adsorption on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ (reaction 15) found in the previous work [16] found to hinder the reaction and give rise to a small negative reaction order in NH₃.

H₂O adsorbs by dative bonding to ionic Cu in a similar way as NH₃. This makes it reasonable to investigate whether H₂O adsorption competes with NO adsorption on Cu^{II} sites similarly to the competition between NH₃ and NO adsorption on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$. Here we investigate H₂O adsorption on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$. The geometry optimized structures in the CHA cage are shown in Fig. 4 (the zeolite framework atoms are removed for clarity).

The adsorption energy of H₂O on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ is calculated to be 0.79 eV. The differential adsorption energy of a second H₂O is 0.62 eV. The O-O bond length in $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ is 1.48 Å in the absence of H₂O. H₂O adsorption does not change the O-O bond length substantially and it is calculated to be 1.46 Å for both structures (A) and (B) in Fig. 4. H₂O can also adsorb on the $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ intermediate and the adsorption energy is 0.59 eV. The stronger adsorption energy on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ as compared to $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ is related to a stable Cu(3d)-O(2p) hybrid orbital, which also results in a short Cu-O bond distance. Because the adsorption energies of NO on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ are 0.70 eV and 0.39 eV, respectively [15,16], H₂O competes with NO for adsorption on these Cu^{II} sites.

The adsorption energy of NH₃ on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ has previously been calculated to be 0.98 eV [16] and the adsorption of NH₃ on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ is here calculated to be 0.66 eV. The adsorption energies for NO, H₂O and NH₃ indicate that H₂O, in similarity

Fig. 3. Proposed reaction cycle for low-temperature NH_3 -SCR over Cu-CHA with water and ammonia adsorption on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$.

with NH_3 , may hinder NO adsorption on Cu^{II} sites and, thereby, reduce the overall SCR activity. To investigate the kinetic consequences of H_2O adsorption, we extend the previously developed [16] reaction cycle with H_2O adsorption/desorption steps, steps 17 and 18 in Fig. 3. Moreover, we also include NH_3 adsorption/desorption on the $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ intermediate (step 19). The kinetic parameters used in the simulations are reported in the Supplementary Material.

The turnover frequency (TOF) from the kinetic simulations are compared to the experiments in Fig. 5. We consider three cases. Case 1 uses the adsorption energies and entropies as evaluated in the DFT calculations. In Case 2, the entropy penalty for water adsorption from the gas phase has been reduced, Case 3 is the result from simulations where in addition to the reduced entropy penalty, a partial pressure-dependent term in the Gibbs free energy of water adsorption has been introduced.

Case 1 shows a decreased TOF with increasing partial pressure of water. However, the dependence is considerably weaker than observed experimentally. The measured strong dependence on the partial pressures of water shows that the inhibition effect of H_2O is stronger than predicted by the applied DFT approach and approximations used to evaluate the kinetic parameters. The results are sensitive to the approximations made in the calculations of the rate constant and it is, for example, not obvious how the entropy changes along the reaction path best should be evaluated. In Case 1 we have used the simple harmonic approximation to evaluate the entropies of the reaction intermediates. The sensitivity to entropy changes, motivates us to investigate the effect of decreasing the entropy loss upon water adsorption. A reduction of the entropy loss corresponds to a case where the adsorbed H_2O molecule has a larger flexibility than predicted by the harmonic approximation. In Case 2, the change in entropy upon adsorption has been reduced from -145 to -107 J/mol K in reaction step 17 and from -131

to -93 J/mol K in reaction step 18 to match the experimental data, by minimizing the mean squared error. The adjusted entropy losses result in a partial pressure dependence of the simulated TOF that align closely with the experimental values, with an R^2 value of 0.95 and a mean squared error of 0.008. Despite the good overall agreement between the experiments and the simulated TOF values in Case 2, the model does not reproduce the experimental results at the highest partial pressures of water.

The low TOF at high partial pressure of water signals an effect that is pressure dependent beyond the logarithmic pressure dependence of the gas-phase entropy. In Case 3, we introduce, in addition to a shift in the entropy, a small linear pressure dependence in the Gibbs free energy of H_2O adsorption (ΔG) expressed as $\Delta G = \alpha P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, where α is 0.161 eV/atm and $P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the partial pressures of water. A linear partial pressure dependence could originate from effective adsorbate-adsorbate interactions in the zeolite, which, in principle, could affect the enthalpy as well as the entropy of the adsorbed state. The pressure dependent term is analogous to the coverage dependent adsorbate-adsorbate interactions for adsorption on solid surfaces. We note that the linear partial pressure dependence is small and amounts to only 0.040 eV at 25% H_2O . The simulated turnover frequency (TOF) using the pressure-dependent Gibbs free energy of adsorption is in good agreement with the experimental data, having an R^2 value of 0.95 and a mean square error of 0.007.

Some previous studies show that low partial pressures of H_2O promote the NH_3 -SCR activity [17,18]. Although the present DFT-based kinetic model shows an inhibiting effect of H_2O at all partial pressures, the model can be adjusted to predict a promoting effect at low partial pressures of H_2O by letting the NH_3 desorption free energy from the peroxo-complex depend on the H_2O partial pressure. However, because of the uncertainty of such dependence at present, we do not include it in this work.

Fig. 4. Structure of (A) one water adsorbed $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ complex, (B) two water molecules adsorbed $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ complex, (C) one water adsorbed $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ complex and (D) one ammonia adsorbed $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ complex. Atomic color codes: Cu (bronze), N (blue), O (red), and H (white).

To investigate the dominating species during the reaction, we have analyzed the partial pressure dependent Cu-speciation (from case 3), Fig. 5(B). A selection of the intermediates are shown where “*” corresponds to an empty Cu-ion (with two NH_3 ligands). The dominant species at low partial pressures of water is $[\text{NH}_3\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ ($\text{NH}_3\text{-OO-}^*$) followed by $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ ($^*\text{-OHOH-}^*$). The concentration of NH_3 -inhibited species decreases at higher partial pressures of H_2O and the dominating species is instead the two H_2O blocked species $[\text{H}_2\text{OCu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ ($\text{H}_2\text{O-OHOH-}^*$) and $[\text{H}_2\text{OCu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ ($\text{H}_2\text{O-OO-}^*$).

The obtained inhibiting effect of H_2O on NH_3 -SCR over Cu-CHA is consistent with NH_3 inhibiting the reaction [16]. The adsorption energy of NH_3 on $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ is higher than the adsorption energy of H_2O , which explains why the $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2(\text{NH}_3)]^{2+}$ state dominates at low H_2O pressures. The inhibiting effect of H_2O on low-temperature NH_3 -SCR over Cu-CHA is consistent with previous measurements [18, 19]. Our interpretation of H_2O -inhibition is slightly different from the one suggested in Ref. [19] where H_2O was proposed to affect the barrier for NO-NH_3 coupling. The two pictures can, however, be reconciled as the barrier for NO-NH_3 coupling in Ref. [19] includes H_2O desorption from the Cu-ion.

Knowing that the two H_2O -blocked configurations $\text{H}_2\text{O-OO-}^*$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O-OHOH-}^*$ dominate at high H_2O partial pressures, it is possible to propose a simple Langmuir-type of expression for the rate of N_2 formation (r_{N_2}):

$$r_{\text{N}_2} = \frac{k_f}{1 + K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} P_{\text{NO}} \quad (6)$$

Where k_f is an effective reaction rate and $K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ an effective equilibrium constant for H_2O adsorption on the Cu-ions. From the DFT-based

kinetic model, we know that $K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ has an exponential pressure dependence. Thus, the effective equilibrium constant can be parameterized according to:

$$K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = a P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} e^{b P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \quad (7)$$

The parameters are fitted to the experimental data to be $k_f = 126.48$ ($\text{s}^{-1}\text{atm}^{-1}$), $a = 8.45 \text{ atm}^{-1}$ and $b = 1.95 \text{ atm}^{-1}$ with an R^2 value of 0.97. The results follow the experimental data closely and the reaction order in H_2O is reported in Fig. 2. The parameter b corresponds to a in the DFT-based kinetic model and are, in fact, similar as $a/k_B T$ is 3.95 atm^{-1} . Note that a Langmuir model with a constant $K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ has a limiting reaction order of -1 .

4. Conclusions

By combining activity measurements and DFT-based microkinetic modeling, we have investigated the effect of H_2O on NH_3 -SCR over Cu-CHA. Water acts as an inhibitor for the NH_3 -SCR reaction with a reaction order that decreases from -0.17 at 2% H_2O to -1.18 at 25% H_2O . The measured reaction order for water follows the simple empirical equation $-3.43 (p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/p^\circ)^{0.76}$, which implies that the reaction order is -1.01 at a partial pressure of 0.2 bar.

DFT calculations reveal that H_2O adsorption on key intermediates such as $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{OHOH}]^{2+}$ competes with NO adsorption. As NO needs to adsorb on the Cu-ions to couple with NH_3 , H_2O inhibits the SCR reaction. The inhibitory effect of H_2O is supported by DFT-based kinetic modeling. The simulated TOF aligns well with experimental data when slight adjustments have been done to the H_2O entropy of adsorption or, alternatively, a weak partial pressure-dependent term in the H_2O Gibbs free energy of adsorption

Fig. 5. (A) Logarithm of simulated TOF as a function of logarithm of the partial pressures of water. The simulations are done for three cases (see main text). (B) Fractional coverage of the dominant surface species for Case 3. The simulations are performed at 200 °C with 600 ppm NH_3 , 500 ppm NO and 10% O_2 and partial pressures of water in the range 2%–25%.

is introduced. The simulations show that H_2O -blocked Cu-complexes are the dominating species at high H_2O pressures. We this information we show that a simple Langmuir model with an equilibrium constant that has a dependence on partial H_2O pressure can describe the experimental data.

Our work gives an atomic-level insight into the mechanism for inhibition of the NH_3 -SCR reaction by water over Cu-CHA catalysts and establishes a clear relationship between the reaction order and the partial pressure of water.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Shivangi Singh: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Yingxin Feng:** Investigation. **Ton V.W. Janssens:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Funding acquisition. **Henrik Grönbeck:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Table with kinetic parameters used in the kinetic simulations. Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2025.116071>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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